

Medication Administration Errors: Prevalence, Causes and Reporting Barriers Among Nurses at Tertiary Care Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

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Abstract

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Aim of the study: This study aimed to determine the frequency of medication administration errors (MAEs), identify key contributing factors, and explore barriers to reporting among healthcare professionals in a clinical setting. Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional descriptive quantitative study was conducted at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi, from January to June 2020. A total of 217 registered nurses (107 males, 110 females; mean age 36 ±5.41 years) with at least one year of clinical experience participated. Non-probability convenience sampling was used. Data were collected using a validated, customized questionnaire covering the

frequency of MAEs, contributing factors, and reporting barriers. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 21.0. Results: The most common MAEs were failure to follow written instructions (53.1%), improper dilution (50.2%), and incorrect labeling (47.9%). The major contributing factors were high workloads (99.5%) and inadequate nursing staff (100.0%). Fear of supervisory reactions (98.2%) and concerns about personal and professional consequences (100.0%) were major barriers to reporting errors. Conclusion: Nursing shortages, excessive workloads, and fear of repercussions significantly contribute to both MAEs and underreporting. Addressing these systemic issues is essential to promoting a safer medication administration environment and enhancing patient safety.

INTRODUCTION

Patient safety must be given top priority in the delivery of healthcare while it is a fundamental right. Most people in the world may use medication at some point in their life to prevent or treat sickness, so safe drug administration is crucial to ensuring patient safety. Improper medicine use, however, may lead to in serious injury, disability, or even death. Patients, healthcare practitioners, and healthcare institutions are all at considerable risk from medication administration errors (MAEs), which are among the most common type of medication errors.¹⁻⁵

Safe and ethical drug administration is a major issue on a globally because it affects patient safety and quality of care. Nurses actively care for patients in the clinical setting and the cornerstone of the healthcare system. Moreover, administering medication to a patient is among the most crucial nursing duties. Approximately 40% of nurses' working hours are spent administering drugs to patients, and their primary responsibility is to do it safely.^{1,4-6}

An error that happens during the course of a procedure that starts when a doctor prescribes a drug and concludes when the patient actually receives it is known as a medication error (ME). Medication administration errors (MAEs) can happen at any point during the prescription, documentation,

dispensing, administration, monitoring, and transcription and documentation phases of the medication-use process. Errors occurred most frequently during administration throughout these phases.⁷

Of the estimated 237 million MEs that occur annually in England, the administrative error rate was 54.4%. In a thorough assessment of MEs in Southeast Asian countries, medication administration errors (MAEs) were likewise found to be the most common kind of ME. The most common type of pharmaceutical errors, known as medicine administration errors, or MAEs, are also the least likely to be detected, which increases the risk of patient harm and places a significant burden on the healthcare system.⁸⁻¹⁰

PURPOSE OF STUDY

This study aimed to determine the prevalence of MAEs, examine their causes, and identify any barriers to reporting them. MAEs are the most common issue in healthcare systems worldwide, and they can result in increased financial waste, longer hospital stays, and higher rates of morbidity and mortality. The results of this study will help in developing and carrying out of focused intervention programs with the objective of reducing the frequency of these errors and enhancing patient safety.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A cross-sectional descriptive quantitative design was performed at the Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi, from January 2020 to June 2020. The study aimed to assess the frequency of medication administration errors (MAEs), identify contributing factors, and explore barriers to reporting them. A total of 217 registered nurses with over one year of clinical experience were selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. The data were gathered using a structured questionnaire organized into four distinct sections: demographic details, common types of medication administration errors (MAEs), factors leading to MAEs, and challenges in reporting these

errors. To ensure the accuracy and dependability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted with 20 nurses who were not included in the main study sample. The outcomes of the pilot test confirmed the questionnaire's reliability and validity, indicating that it was a suitable and consistent tool for data collection in the research.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study received ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. They were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any stage without any negative consequences. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 21.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). Descriptive statistics—such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations—were employed to summarize and interpret categorical and continuous variables. The research focused on determining the prevalence of medication administration errors (MAEs), identifying contributing factors at both organizational and individual levels, and recognizing significant barriers to error reporting. The results underscore the importance of regular nursing education sessions and workshops aimed at strengthening clinical skills, promoting patient safety, and reducing medication errors in healthcare settings.

RESULTS

A total of 217 nurses participated in this study, with demographic data summarized in **Table 1**. The majority of participants were female (50.7%) and within the age range of 30–40 years (53.5%). Most nurses were satisfied with their career (97.7%) and had extensive experience, with a mean of 12.4 years in the field. **Table 2** outlines the most common medication administration errors

(MAEs) encountered by nurses. The most frequent errors included administering medications at the wrong time (40.6%) and inaccuracies in dilution rates (50.2%). Other significant errors included poor labeling (47.9%) and difficulty in recognizing doctors' handwritten instructions (53.0%).

Table 3 highlights the primary causes of MAEs, with a shortage of nursing staff (100%) and workplace discrimination (95.9%) being the leading factors. Poor knowledge about drugs (67.3%) and inadequate documentation (75.1%) were also significant contributors. Environmental factors, such as improper lighting and noise (89.9%), and heavy patient loads (99.5%), were recognized as major causes.

Finally, **Table 4** presents the barriers to reporting MAEs. The most significant barriers included fear of disciplinary actions (87.6%), poor monitoring systems (86.6%), and a lack of knowledge on how to report errors (87.6%). Other barriers included fear of reactions from co-workers (77.4%), forgetfulness in reporting (74.7%), and concerns about supervisor reactions (98.2%). Nurses also reported a tendency to neglect the importance of reporting MAEs (59.9%).

DISCUSSION

Nurses play a critical role in the medication administration process, as they are directly involved in patient care and administering medications.¹¹⁻¹³ The results of this study, conducted at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center in Karachi in 2020, shed light on various factors contributing to medication administration errors (MAEs) among nurses. The mean age of the participants was 36 years ($SD \pm 5.41$), suggesting a relatively homogeneous age group. In comparison, a similar study conducted in South Korea reported mean ages of 45.5 and 34.6 years, indicating that age could play a significant role in MAEs. Older nurses, with more years of experience, may have better knowledge and skills, which could reduce the likelihood of errors.¹¹ However, this does not

entirely exclude the impact of other factors, such as a lack of sufficient training or knowledge gaps, which were also identified as primary contributors to MAEs in this study.

The findings of this study align with previous research conducted by Samsiah et al. (2016), who suggested that the level of nursing education significantly influences the occurrence of MAEs. The study highlights the importance of nursing education in shaping both patient care and the overall hospital environment.¹²⁻¹⁵ The absence of structured policies for medication administration and a lack of a robust monitoring system at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center are concerning. Similar studies conducted in Iranian and American hospitals have pointed out the need for clear guidelines and monitoring systems for MAEs. In these studies, researchers emphasized that having formalized policies and established procedures is a critical factor in reducing and controlling MAEs.¹⁶⁻²¹

As indicated in **Table 3**, the most common causes of MAEs in this study include a shortage of nursing staff (100%), poor knowledge of drugs (67.3%), inadequate documentation (75.1%), and poor communication of doctors' instructions (61.3%). These findings underscore the importance of addressing systemic issues, such as insufficient staffing, lack of proper training, and errors in documentation, to reduce the risk of MAEs. Furthermore, **Table 4** outlines several barriers to reporting MAEs, including fear of disciplinary actions (87.6%), lack of knowledge on how to report errors (87.6%), and concerns about the reaction from coworkers (77.4%). These barriers highlight the need for a more supportive and transparent reporting culture in healthcare settings. Nurses are less likely to report errors if they fear retribution or if they are not provided with adequate training on how to document and report MAEs. Ultimately, addressing both the root causes and the barriers to reporting medication errors is essential for improving patient safety. This study

emphasizes the importance of creating a more supportive work environment through improved training, clear policies, and a monitoring system to reduce MAEs and foster a culture of openness regarding medication errors.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores that nursing staff shortages and high workload levels are critical barriers to effective reporting of medication administration errors (MAEs) among nurses. Addressing these issues by increasing the number of nursing staff in wards could significantly reduce workload and improve reporting behaviors, ultimately enhancing patient safety outcomes. Additionally, the lack of proper training and knowledge about medication administration was identified as a key factor contributing to MAEs. Therefore, facilitating continuous nursing education courses or workshops focused on medication safety, error reporting, and clinical skills development could play a crucial role in empowering nurses with the necessary knowledge and confidence to report errors and improve their practice. This finding suggests that healthcare institutions should prioritize adequate nurse staffing and invest in ongoing professional development as foundational strategies to support safer and more effective clinical environments.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: None

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APPENDIX

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF NURSES IN JINNAH POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL CENTER, KARACHI (N=217)

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	107	49.3
	Female	110	50.7
Age	21-30	53	24.4
	30-40	116	53.5
	41-50	48	22.1
	Mean 36 years (SD±5.41)		
	Single	34	15.7
Marital status	Married	177	81.6
	Widow(er) or divorced	6	2.8
	Yes	129	59.4
Worked in more than 1 hospital	No	88	40.6
	Don't know	0	0.0%
Satisfied with nursing career	Yes	212	97.7
	No	5	2.3
	Don't know	0	0.0%
Had an unrelated second job	Yes	121	55.8
	No	96	44.2
Shift type	Don't know	0	0.0%
	Morning	124	57.1
	Evening	41	18.9
	Night	52	24.4
Qualification	Registered	118	54.4
	Nurse		

	Bachelor's Degree	89	41.0
	Master's Degree	10	4.6
	1-5	44	20.3
	6-10	57	26.3
Working experience	11-15	41	18.9
	16-25	75	34.6
	Mean 12.396 years (SD±5.52)		
	<50000	85	39.2
Socio-economic status	>50000	132	60.8

TABLE 2: MOST COMMON MEDICATION ADMINISTRATION ERRORS AMONG NURSES AT JINNAH POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL CENTER, KARACHI (N=217).

Variable	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Don't know n (%)
Medication administer at the wrong time	88(40.6%)	129(59.4%)	0(0.0%)
Medication administer wrong dose	25(11.5%)	182(83.9%)	10(4.6%)
Administer inaccurate dilution rate of medication	109(50.2%)	108(49.8%)	0(0.0%)
Medication administer by using the wrong route of	22(10.1%)	182(83.9%)	13(6.0%)
Administer medication to the wrong patient	7(3.2%)	199(91.7%)	11(5.1%)
Inappropriate labeling of medications	104(47.9%)	113(52.1%)	0(0.0%)
Verbal or order on telephone by the physician/doctor	79(36.4%)	138(63.6%)	0(0.0%)

Doctors' written instruction (prescription) is hard to recognize 115(53.0%) 102(47.0%) 0(0.0%)

TABLE 3: MOST COMMON CAUSE OF MEDICATION ADMINISTRATION ERROR AT JINNAH POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL CENTER, KARACHI (N=217).

Variable	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Don't know n (%)
Shortage of nursing staff in the wards	217(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)
Discrimination in the workplace	208(95.9%)	9(4.1%)	0(0.0%)
Improper documentation record when patients are shifted to other wards	163(75.1%)	43(19.8%)	11(5.1%)
Poor knowledge regarding drug in wards	146(67.3%)	71(32.7%)	0(0.0%)
Improper convey doctors' instruction (order) and improper documentation in record	133(61.3%)	84(38.7%)	0(0.0%)
Poor knowledge about medication	110(50.7%)	107(49.3%)	0(0.0%)
Job dissatisfaction	133(61.3%)	84(38.7%)	0(0.0%)
Economic problems	100(46.1%)	117(53.9%)	0(0.0%)
Family problems	103(47.5%)	114(52.5%)	0(0.0%)
Psychological and emotional problems	64(29.5%)	153(70.5%)	0(0.0%)
Over time is the result of tiredness and Fatigue in wards	175(80.6%)	42(19.4%)	0(0.0%)
Type of shift work	214(98.6%)	3(1.4%)	0(0.0%)
Look-a-like medications	158(72.8%)	53(24.4%)	6(2.8%)

Availability of variety of medication in wards	121(55.8%)	85(39.2%)	11(5.1%)
Inappropriate behavior of patients	182(83.9%)	35(16.1%)	0(0.0%)
Presence of patients' companions in wards	154(71.0%)	63(29.0%)	0(0.0%)
Excessive number of patients admitted in wards with severe illness	212(97.7%)	5(2.3%)	0(0.0%)
Heavy workload due to the admitted excessive number of patients in wards	216(99.5%)	1(0.5%)	0(0.0%)
MAEs is the result of environmental condition of wards (e.g. improper light, ventilation and temperature)	195(89.9%)	22(10.1%)	0(0.0%)
Excessive/ loud noise in wards	138(63.6%)	79(36.4%)	0(0.0%)
Drug arrangement on the shelves	190(87.6%)	27(12.4%)	0(0.0%)

TABLE 4: TYPES OF BARRIER REPORTING AT JINNAH POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL CENTER, KARACHI (N=217).

Variable	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Don't know n (%)
Poor recording and reporting of MAEs in health care system	146(67.3%)	71(32.7%)	0(0.0%)
Poor monitoring and supervisory mechanism in healthcare system	188(86.6%)	29(13.4%)	0(0.0%)
Lack of information about how to report MAEs	190(87.6%)	21(9.7%)	1(.5%)
Fear of disciplinary/punishment	190(87.6%)	27(12.4%)	0(0.0%)

actions

Afraid of the reaction from co-workers	168(77.4%)	49(22.6%)	0(0.0%)
Not giving priority to report MAEs after occurring	130(59.9%)	87(40.1%)	0(0.0%)
Fear about the head nurse /ward in-charge/ supervisor reaction	213(98.2%)	4(1.8%)	0(0.0%)
Worry and tense about the MAEs consequences	217(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)
Forget to report MAEs to the head nurse/ ward in-charge/supervisor	162(74.7%)	31(14.3%)	24(11.1%)
Attitude and behavior of nurses	96(44.2%)	65(30%)	56(25.8%)
